

Conversions of units of stomatal conductance and CO₂ concentration

Xuejun Dong

Texas A&M AgriLife Research - Uvalde

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Unit conversion for leaf boundary layer resistance

Let's verify that the value of leaf boundary layer resistance $r_b = 0.18 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s mol}^{-1}$ for Eq. A5 of Farquhar et al. (1980)¹¹ is equivalent to 0.07 s cm^{-1} . Because the unit of r_b comes from the definition of conductance, what we need to do is to convert the mol of water vapor into equivalent unit of volume (m^3). To do this, we assume temperature T of 293 K (20 °C), and atmospheric pressure P of $1.013 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}$ (= 1 atm). Using the ideal gas law ($R = 8.314 \text{ m}^3 \text{ Pa mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), we can find the volume of 1 mol water vapor is $1 \times RT/P = 0.02405 \text{ m}^3$.

Then, $r_b = 0.18 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s mol}^{-1} = \frac{0.18}{0.02405 \times 100} = 0.075 \text{ s cm}^{-1}$.

¹¹G. D. Farquhar, E.-D. Schulze and M. Küppers. 1980. Responses to humidity by stomatal of *Nicotiana glauca* L. and *Corylus avellana* L. are consistent with the optimization of carbon dioxide uptake with respect to water loss. Aust. J. Plant Physiol. 7: 315-327.

Conversion from CO₂ concentration (ppm) to CO₂ partial pressure (Pa)

Let's show how to convert the atmospheric CO₂ concentration in ppm to CO₂ partial pressure. To do this, we need to use the ideal gas law:

$$P = RT \left(\frac{n}{V} \right).$$

Suppose at 20 °C, in dry air (density²⁹ of 1.204 kg m⁻³, and molar mass of 28.97 g/mol), the CO₂ concentration is 425 ppm (or μmol [CO₂]/mol [air]). The corresponding CO₂ partial pressure can be computed as:

$$P = 8.314 \times 293.15 \times \left(\frac{425 \times 10^{-6}}{28.97/1204} \right) = 43.05 \text{ Pa},$$

where R is 8.314 m³ Pa mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, T is 293.15 K (= 273.15 + 20.00). If the air is saturated (density 1.194 kg m⁻³ at 20 °C), $P = 42.69$ Pa.

²⁹See next page on how air density is related to T , P and molar masses.

Calculation of air density

The density of air can be calculated using the following formula³⁰:

$$\rho = \frac{p_d M_d + p_v M_v}{RT},$$

where ρ is air density (kg m^{-3}), p_d is partial pressure of dry air (Pa), M_d is molar mass of dry air ($0.02897 \text{ kg mol}^{-1}$), p_v is pressure of water vapor (Pa), M_v is molar mass of water vapor ($0.01802 \text{ kg mol}^{-1}$), R is universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), and T absolute temperature (K). For air with varying degrees of humidity, p_v is calculated as $p_v = \phi p_{\text{sat}}$, where ϕ is relative humidity (RH) and p_{sat} (Pa) is saturate vapor pressure:

$$p_{\text{sat}} = 610.78 \exp\left(\frac{17.27(T - 273.15)}{T - 35.85}\right),$$

where T is absolute temperature (K).

³⁰Based on https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Density_of_air.

Calculation of air density - continuing

When air is completely dry, $p_v = 0$ in the above equation of air density; on the other hand, when air is saturated, $p_v = p_{\text{sat}}$, and $p_d = p - p_v$, where p is the atmospheric pressure (at sea level it is 101325 Pa).

Exercises:

(1) Use a calculator or a computer spreadsheet to verify the numerical values of air density (kg m^{-3}) under selected temperature/humidity conditions at sea level.

(2) Contemplate on the results and compare them with your intuitions about the density of dry and humid air.

Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Dry air	Moist air (50% RH)	Saturate air
20	1.204	1.199	1.194
40	1.127	1.112	1.096